

Hospital Based Observational Assessment of Carrying Angle Changes Following Supracondylar Humeral Fractures in Children

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of the study was to evaluate the functional outcome of carrying angle changes following supracondylar humeral fractures in children.

Methods: The present study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedic for one year and 100 patients were included in the study.

Results: A total of 100 patients with a mean age of 5.2 years (SD± 2.3) were seen. 75% were male and 60% were less than 5 years of age. Most of the injuries occurred at home (64%). A total of 72% of the patients were seen within 24 hours of the injury. There was a significant difference in mean scores of PedsQL (all P values < .01) at 6 months. In the present study, pin site infection complication was seen in 5 patients.

Conclusion: In this prospective study, the quality of life of patients following SCHF diminished at the time of the injury and returned to the population normal 6 months after. There was no significant difference in HRQoL scores between patients who presented early and those who presented late. The delayed presentation and management did not also affect the functional outcome and complications.

Keywords: Flynn Criteria, Outcome, PedsQL, Supracondylar Humeral Fracture.

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Introduction

Fractures around the elbow constitute one in three paediatric fractures. [1] The incidence of paediatric fractures involving the elbow is increasing. [2] The narrow supracondylar region is at a risk of fracture due to the presence of the olecranon fossa posteriorly and the coronoid fossa anteriorly. Supracondylar fracture is a metaphyseal injury, almost exclusively seen in the immature skeleton, mostly in children under ten years. [3] Furthermore, ligamentous laxity with hyperextension of the elbow is common in the growing skeleton, focusing a bending force on the susceptible supracondylar area. [3] Following supracondylar fracture in children, residual deformity can remodel well if it is the sagittal plane. [3,4] It is important to achieve anatomical reduction in the coronal plane as residual deformity here is less likely to remodel. Forms of treatment for these fractures include casting, traction, open reduction, and closed reduction with percutaneous

pinning (CRPP). There is a trend towards operative fixation in all displaced fractures [5] usually with CRPP, the incidence of which increased fivefold between 1987 and 2010. [6,7] However, there is no consensus of opinion regarding the optimal treatment. [4,8]

Some authors, however, have found no variations among the sexes whereas others found higher incidence among girls. [9,10] The left hand (which usually is the non dominant hand) is mostly affected in most studies. [9-11] These fractures are classified using the Gartland classification, which also serves as a treatment guide. [12] Gartland types I and II a fractures may be managed non operatively whereas types IIb and III are treated operatively. [13-15] Closed reduction and percutaneous (CRPP) fixation using Kirschner wires (K-wires) is the operative treatment of choice. [16] Bahk et al., in 2008 devised a classification based on fracture patterns in the

coronal and sagittal plane and proposed pin configuration specific to fracture pattern. The Bahk classification is based on the angle the fracture line makes with the line perpendicular to the distal humerus axis. In the anteroposterior (AP) view this is described as “coronal obliquity” and in the lateral view as “sagittal obliquity”. Coronal obliquity $>10^\circ$ (medial oblique and lateral oblique varieties) are associated with more comminutions and rotational malalignments. Sagittal obliquities $>20^\circ$ (high sagittal) are associated with rotational mal-unions and associated with other injuries. [17]

The aim of the study was to evaluate the functional outcome of carrying angle changes following supracondylar humeral fractures in children.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of Orthopaedic, Jawahar Lal Nehru medical College & Hospital, Bhagalpur, Bihar, India for one year and 100 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria for this study were children up to the age of 13 years. Children who had SCHF that were over 3 weeks old were excluded.

Study procedure

Patients with Gartland type I fractures did not need any form of manipulation, whereas those with type II a fractures had manipulation under anesthesia. The limb was then put in a well- padded long-arm splint with 60° to 70° of elbow flexion for 3 weeks. X-rays were obtained weekly to ensure the fracture remains reduced. The higher energy types are usually associated with gross deformity of the elbow. All cases of Gartland type IIb and type III were done using CRPP with the aid of an image intensifier. The limb was then splinted for 3 weeks after which time the k-wires were removed. The cross-pinning technique was mostly used for this study. None of these injuries needed open reduction and pinning and none of those managed nonsurgical redislocated.

Results

Table 1: Characteristics of patients

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	75	75
Female	25	25
Age		
Less than 5 years	60	60
More than 5 years	40	40
Mode of transport		
Public: (taxi, trotro)	65	65
Private cars	25	25
Walk-in	8	8
Ambulance	2	2
Location where the injury occurred		
Home	64	64
School	28	28
Recreational area	8	8
Time injury occurred		
Day (morning and afternoon) Night (evening and night)	34	34
Injury to admission		
Less than 24 hours	72	72
24 hours to 72 hours	10	10
4 hours to 14 days	18	18
Injury to theatre		
Less than 24 hours	34	34
24 hours to 72 hours	10	10
4 hours to 14 days	56	56

A total of 100 patients with a mean age of 5.2 years (SD \pm 2.3) were seen. 75% were male and 60% were less than 5 years of age. Most of the injuries occurred at home (64%). A total of 72% of the patients were seen within 24 hours of the injury.

Table 2: Complications observed during the study period

Complications	N
Pin site infection	5
Gartland type II	2
Gartland type III	3
Nerve injury	4
AIN	2
Ulna nerve	1
Vascular injury	1
Cubitus varus	1
Myositis ossificans	1

In the present study, pin site infection complication was seen in 5 patients.

Discussion

Supracondylar humeral fractures (SCHF) are the most common pediatric elbow fractures. [20-22] The reported incidence is between 50% and 70% of elbow fractures [23] and about 13% of all pediatric fractures. [24] The peak incidence is between the ages of 5 to 7 years with a male-to-female ratio of 2:1. [25,26]

A total of 100 patients with a mean age of 5.2 years (SD± 2.3) were seen. 75% were male and 60% were less than 5 years of age. Most of the injuries occurred at home (64%). A total of 72% of the patients were seen within 24 hours of the injury. The type II fractures in our series, whether managed surgically or nonsurgically, all resulted in satisfactory outcomes. This was because we applied the right treatment protocols depending on the fracture type (manipulation and splinting for type IIa and CRPP for type IIb). Miranda et al [27] made the same observations as they reported similar radiological and functional outcomes when closed reduction followed by casting was compared to CRPP of type II fractures. Again, 77% of type II fractures in the series by Hadlow et al [28] would have had unnecessary surgery if all of these fractures were surgically treated. Moraleda et al [29] also reported a good outcome (80.4%) in a series of 46 patients managed nonsurgically for type II fractures with a mean follow-up of 6.6 years.

There was a significant difference in mean scores of PedsQL (all P values < .01) at 6 months. In the present study, pin site infection complication was seen in 5 patients. Our results suggests that all the components of the PedsQL were affected by the injury initially but improved to near the population normal at 6 months' follow-up. This may be explained by the fact that it took about 3 to 4 weeks for the fracture to heal clinically and subsequent use of the affected limb with full return to activities of daily living. According to Michelson et al [30] by ages 5 to 6 years, most children would have enrolled into schools compared with those younger than this age. This age is also associated with

increased activity levels, minimal supervision by parents, increased playground activity both at school and home, all of which increases the risk of sustaining fractures. [31,32]

The role of home environment cannot be over-emphasized as 64% of the SCHF in our study occurred at home and this is similar to that found by Mangwani et al. [33] This may be because most of the patients from this study were restricted to play at home mostly because of safety reasons or lack of availability of sports facilities in the areas. Of these fractures, 66% occurred during the daytime, which unsurprisingly coincides with the period of maximum activity, and less supervision as the parents may not be home or the child may be in school. In this study, we fixed the fractures with 2 crossed pins. The crossing of pins at the fracture site may be associated with secondary displacement of the fracture and this might have accounted for the single incidence of cubitus varus seen. This was not serious enough to warrant surgical correction. Research has shown that cross pinning provides much stability compared with lateral or parallel pinning thereby reducing the incidence of cubitus varus which may result from displacement of the distal fragment or post treatment loss of reduction. [34,35] There was a single case of vascular injury that resolved after CRPP as well as a case of myositis ossificans, which resolved within a year of the injury. There were however no cases of compartment syndrome or Volkmann ischemic contractures, same as reported by other authors. [36]

Conclusion

In this prospective study, the quality of life of patients following SCHF diminished at the time of the injury and returned to the population normal 6 months after. There was no significant difference in HRQoL scores between patients who presented early and those who presented late. The delayed presentation and management did not also affect the functional outcome and complications. Therefore, in a lower or lower middle income country surgical management of these injuries after late presentation is still safe.

References

1. Cheng JC, Ng BK, Ying SY, Lam PK. A 10-year study of the changes in the pattern and treatment of 6,493 fractures. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 1999 May 1;19(3): 344-50.
2. Helenius I, Lamberg TS, Kääriäinen S, Impinen A, Pakarinen MP. Operative treatment of fractures in children is increasing: a population-based study from Finland. *JBJS*. 2009 Nov 1;91(11):2612-6.
3. Marquis CP, Cheung G, Dwyer JS, Emery DF. Supracondylar fractures of the humerus. *Current Orthopaedics*. 2008 Feb 1;22(1):62-9.
4. Omid R, Choi PD, Skaggs DL. Supracondylar humeral fractures in children. *JBJS*. 2008 May 1;90(5):1121-32.
5. Ladenhauf HN, Schaffert M, Bauer J. The displaced supracondylar humerus fracture: indications for surgery and surgical options: a 2014 update. *Current opinion in pediatrics*. 2014 Feb 1;26(1):64-9.
6. Salonen A, Pajulo O, Lahdes-Vasama T, Välipakka J, Mattila VM. Increased incidence of distal humeral fractures and surgical treatment in 0- to 18-year-old patients treated in Finland from 1987 to 2010. *Journal of children's orthopaedics*. 2013 Dec;7(6):559-64.
7. Woratanarat P, Angsanuntsukh C, Rattanasiri S, Attia J, Woratanarat T, Thakkinstian A. Meta-analysis of pinning in supracondylar fracture of the humerus in children. *Journal of orthopaedic trauma*. 2012 Jan 1;26(1):48-53.
8. Miranda I, Sánchez-Arteaga P, Marrachelli VG, Miranda FJ, Salom M. Orthopedic versus surgical treatment of Gartland type II supracondylar humerus fracture in children. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics B*. 2014 Jan 1;23(1):93-9.
9. Farnsworth CL, Silva PD, Mubarak SJ. Etiology of supracondylar humerus fractures. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 1998 Jan 1;18(1):38-42.
10. Houshian S, Mehdi B, Larsen MS. The epidemiology of elbow fracture in children: analysis of 355 fractures, with special reference to supracondylar humerus fractures. *Journal of orthopaedic science*. 2001 Jul; 6:3 12-5.
11. Topping RE, Blanco JS, Davis TJ. Clinical evaluation of crossed-pin versus lateral-pin fixation in displaced supracondylar humerus fractures. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 1995 Jul 1;15(4):435-9.
12. GARTLAND J. Management of supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children. *Surgery, gynecology & obstetrics*. 1959 Aug;109(2) :145-54.
13. Parikh SN, Wall EJ, Foad S, Wiersema B, Nolte B. Displaced type II extension supracondylar humerus fractures: do they all need pinning? *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 2004 Jul 1;24(4):380-4.
14. Mehlman CT, Crawford AH, McMillion TL, Roy DR. Operative treatment of supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children: the Cincinnati experience. *Acta Orthopaedica Belgica*. 1996 Jan 1; 62:41-50.
15. Skaggs DL, Hale JM, Bassett J, Kaminsky C, Kay RM, Tolo VT. Operative treatment of supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children: the consequences of pin placement. *JBJS*. 2001 May 1;83(5):735-40.
16. Ponce BA, Hedequist DJ, Zurakowski D, Atkinson CC, Waters PM. Complications and timing of follow-up after closed reduction and percutaneous pinning of supracondylar humerus fractures: follow-up after percutaneous pinning of supracondylar humerus fractures. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 2004 Nov 1;24(6):610-4.
17. Bahk MS, Srikumaran U, Ain MC, Erkula G, Leet AI, Sargent MC, Sponseller PD. Patterns of pediatric supracondylar humerus fractures. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 2008 Jul-Aug;28(5):493-9.
18. Harris PA, Taylor R, Thielke R, Payne J, Gonzalez N, Conde JG. Research electronic data capture (REDCap)—a metadata-driven methodology and workflow process for providing translational research informatics support. *Journal of biomedical informatics*. 2009 Apr 1;42(2):377-81.
19. Harris PA, Taylor R, Minor BL, et al. The REDCap consortium: Building an international community of software platform partners. *J Biomed Inform*. 2019; 95:103208.
20. Dimeglio A. Growth in pediatric orthopaedics. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 2001; 21:549-555.
21. Cheng JC, Ng BK, Ying SY, et al. A 10-year study of the changes in the pattern and treatment of 6 493 fractures. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 1999; 19:344-350.
22. Otsuka NY, Kasser JR. Supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children. *J Am Acad Orthop Surg*. 1997; 5:19-26.
23. Wilson MJ, Hunter JB. Supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children—wire removal in the outpatient setting. *Injury Extra*. 2006; 37:313-315.
24. Omid R, Choi PD, Skaggs DL. Supracondylar humeral fractures in children. *J Bone Joint Surg Am*. 2008; 90:1121-1132.
25. Cheng JC, Lam TP, Maffulli N. Epidemiological features of supracondylar fractures of the humerus in Chinese children. *J Pediatr Orthop B*. 2001; 10:63-67.
26. Farnsworth CL, Silva PD, Mubarak SJ. Etiology of supracondylar humerus fractures. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 1998; 18:38-42.
27. Miranda I, Sánchez-Arteaga P, Marrachelli VG, Miranda FJ, Salom M. Orthopedic versus

- surgical treatment of Gartland type II supracondylar humerus fracture in children. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics B*. 2014 Jan 1;23(1):93-9.
28. Hadlow AT, Devane P, Nicol RO. A selective treatment approach to supracondylar fracture of the humerus in children. *Journal of Pediatric Orthopaedics*. 1996 Jan 1;16(1):104-6.
 29. Moraleda L, Valencia M, Barco R, González-Moran G. Natural history of unreduced Gartland type-II supracondylar fractures of the humerus in children: a two to thirteen-year follow-up study. *JBJS*. 2013 Jan 2;95(1):28-34.
 30. Mitchelson AJ, Illingworth KD, Robinson BS, Elnimeiry KA, Wilson CJ, Markwell SJ, Gabriel KR, McGinty J, Saleh KJ. Patient demographics and risk factors in pediatric distal humeral supracondylar fractures. *Orthopedics*. 2013 Jun 1;36(6):e700-6.
 31. Gofin R, Donchin M, Schulrof B. Motor ability: protective or risk for school injuries? *Accident Analysis & Prevention*. 2004 Jan 1;36(1):43-8.
 32. Spinks AB, Scott D, Bain CJ, Nagle CM, Macpherson AK, McClure RJ. Parental attitudes to supervision and risk of childhood injury: results from a primary school cohort. *International Journal of Injury Control & Safety Promotion*. 2008 Mar 1;15(1):49-52.
 33. Mangwani J, Nadarajah R, Paterson JM. Supracondylar humeral fractures in children: Ten Years' Experience In A Teaching Hospital. *The Journal of Bone & Joint Surgery British Volume*. 2006 Mar 1;88(3):362-5.
 34. Hussain S, Gul M, Dhar S. Open reduction and internal fixation of displaced proximal humerus fractures with AO Stainless Steel T-Plate. *Malays Orthop J*. 2014; 8:8–13.
 35. Pretell-Mazzini J, Rodriguez-Martin J, Aunon-Martin I, et al. Controversial topics in the management of displaced supracondylar humerus fractures in children. *Strategies Trauma Limb Reconstr*. 2011; 6:43–50.
 36. Li M, Xu J, Hu T, et al. Surgical management of Gartland type III supracondylar humerus fractures in older children: a retrospective study. *J Pediatr Orthop B*. 2019; 28:530–535.